

ISCHEMIC STROKE

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ABSTRACT

Ischemic stroke is a growing medical, social and economic problem, the scope of which is becoming epidemic (Graeme J.H., 2016). Despite relatively stable incidence rates and a decrease in mortality over the past two decades, there has been an increase in the number of years of life adjusted for disability and stroke-related deaths (Feigin V.L. et al., 2014). Despite the undoubted achievements in this area, the problem of the negative impact of neurological deficit on the effectiveness of rehabilitation measures, short-term and long-term prognosis, functional status and quality of life of patients does not become less significant. (Klipper E. et al., 2016).

The relevance of the problem.

The problem of cerebral stroke remains extremely relevant at the present time, which is determined by the significant frequency of its development, a high percentage of disability and mortality of patients. Over the past 10 years, the incidence rate of ONMC has reached 2.5 - 3.0 per 1000 population. Cardiocerebral embolism causes the development of 30-40% of all cases of ischemic stroke. Cardioembolic stroke (CEI) is often associated with severe neurological disorders and significantly worsens the quality of life of patients. The risk of relapse is also quite high. Therefore, timely recognition of the cardiac cause of stroke and determination of the optimal prevention strategy are so relevant[2].

Cardioembolic stroke (CEI) is a clinical syndrome that develops due to a critical

decrease in blood supply to a part of the brain in a certain arterial basin, which leads to ischemia with the formation of a focus of acute necrosis of brain tissue – a cerebral infarction. Most often, ischemic stroke develops as a result of thrombosis or embolism in cerebral atherosclerosis or as a result of cardiogenic embolism.

Cardioembolic stroke (30% of all ischemic strokes) develops due to cardiocerebral embolism in heart diseases. Thrombotic masses in the left atrium, ventricle, and valvular apparatus of the heart are an embologenic substrate, when detached from which the embolus is transferred to the arterial system of the brain.

Sources of high risk of cerebral vascular embolism (Adams H.P. et al., 1993):

-Artificial heart valve;

-Mitral stenosis with atrial fibrillation;

- Permanent form of atrial fibrillation;
- Left atrial thrombus;
- Left ventricular thrombus;
- Sinus node weakness syndrome;
- Acute period of myocardial infarction (up to 4 weeks);
- Dilated cardiomyopathy;
- Left ventricular akinesia;
- Atrial myxoma;
- Infectious endocarditis.

Treatment in the acute period of CEI

In the treatment of CEI, undifferentiated (basic) and differentiated therapy is distinguished, taking into account the etiology and pathogenesis of this subtype of ischemic stroke.

Stroke therapy should be started as early as possible - in the first 3-6 hours of the disease (the period of the "therapeutic window"). Early initiation of therapy and early rehabilitation of the patient help to significantly reduce mortality and the degree of disability of patients. The combination of urgent measures in the acute period of stroke and early intensive rehabilitation makes it possible to ensure that only 5-6% of stroke patients need constant care.

Basic therapy

Undifferentiated AI therapy is aimed at maintaining the basic vital functions of the body. It includes ensuring adequate breathing, maintaining blood circulation, monitoring and correction of water-electrolyte disorders, reducing brain edema, prevention and treatment of pneumonia and pulmonary embolism. The development of somatic complications significantly complicates the early rehabilitation of the patient and often leads to death, accounting for about half of the causes of death in the acute period of stroke.

In cases of coma or respiratory failure in a stroke patient, sanitation and airway patency are necessary. Inhalation of oxygen (2-4 liters per minute) through a nasal catheter is indicated, especially with insufficient oxygen saturation of the blood. If there are difficulties or respiratory arrest, aspiration of vomit, then endotracheal intubation with artificial ventilation of the lungs is performed.

With the development of heart failure, myocardial infarction or arrhythmia, a cardiologist's consultation and additional treatment on his recommendation are necessary. In cases of arterial hypotension, which is rare in stroke and is more often caused by concomitant cardiac pathology, dehydration or overdose of hypotensive agents, infusion of blood-replacing solutions (albumin, polyglucine) or low-molecular dextran solutions in combination with corticosteroids (120-150 mg prednisolone or 8-12 mg dexamethasone) is recommended. If there is no effect, 50-100 mg of dopamine per 200-400 ml of saline solution is used intravenously (at first 3-6 drops per minute). Optimal maintenance of blood pressure (BP) at a level not lower than 140-160 /80-90 mm Hg.

Arterial hypertension on the first day of stroke is noted in most patients with ischemic stroke. Tactics in relation to increased blood pressure in a patient in the acute period of AI has its own characteristics. In the first days of a stroke, autoregulation of cerebral blood flow is disrupted, therefore, with a decrease in blood pressure, there is no adequate expansion of the brain arteries and perfusion pressure in the ischemic tissue drops, which can lead to additional cell death in the area of the so-called ischemic

penumbra. The risk of hemorrhagic transformation of a cerebral infarction, an increase in cerebral edema and an increase in intracranial pressure increases while maintaining high blood pressure values, but is considered less significant than the risk of additional cerebral ischemia. When conducting hypotensive therapy on the first day of a stroke, a gradual and moderate decrease in blood pressure is recommended in order to establish systolic pressure at 10 mm above the “working” figures, diastolic — no higher than 120 mm Hg, in the case of newly diagnosed hypertension.

After 7-10 days, it is necessary to select antihypertensive drugs with gradual correction of blood pressure, because it has been convincingly shown that gradual normalization of blood pressure significantly reduces the risk of repeated disorders of cerebral circulation. [1].

Cerebral edema is a formidable complication of AI and can lead to an increase in intracranial pressure and, as a consequence, to dislocation and compression of cerebral structures. Treatment of brain edema is indicated in stroke patients with impaired consciousness or progression of neurological disorders caused by increasing brain edema. In these cases, it is recommended to raise the head end of the bed, limit the introduction of fluid to 1 liter per day. Glycerol is used from medications (inside a 10% solution at a dose of 0.25–1 g / kg every 4-6 hours). or intravenously drip 10% on a saline solution at the rate of 1-2 ml / kg for 2 hours) or osmotic diuretics (2 times a day rheogluman, mannitol 15% - 200 ml IV drip, after 10-15 minutes lasix 20 mg IV), or dexamethasone (intravenously at an initial dose of 8 mg,

and then at a dose of 4 mg every 6 hours) - in the absence of severe forms of diabetes mellitus, internal bleeding, malignant arterial hypertension. Controlled hyperventilation of the lungs is also performed to reduce brain edema.

During intensive therapy, it is necessary to ensure normal water-salt metabolism, which requires monitoring the moisture of the skin and tongue, skin turgor, hematocrit and electrolytes in the blood serum, and in case of violations – corrective therapy. Fluid restriction or irrational use of diuretics leads to dehydration, which contributes to an increase in blood clotting and a decrease in blood pressure. Excessive fluid injection during infusion therapy may increase cerebral edema.

Of great importance is the maintenance of normoglycemia, in diabetic patients it may be necessary to change the usual therapy (temporary switch to insulin, increase or decrease the dose of insulin)[3,4].

An increase in body temperature, which worsens the outcome of a stroke, is more often caused by pneumonia or urinary tract infection, which requires adequate antibacterial therapy. For the prevention of pneumonia, breathing exercises (deep breathing) and early activation of the patient are recommended.

To reduce headaches, non-narcotic analgesics are used, for example 500 mg of paracetamol every 4-6 hours.

In cases of recurrent vomiting and persistent hiccups, metoclopramide 10 mg intravenously (intramuscularly) or orally 2-4 times a day, haloperidol 10-20 drops (1.5–2 mg) per day can be used[5].

Anticonvulsants are prescribed to relieve epileptic seizures.

With psychomotor agitation, 10-20 mg of diazepam is used intravenously or intramuscularly, 2-4 g of sodium oxybutyrate intravenously or 5-10 mg of haloperidol intravenously or intramuscularly.

Patients with impaired consciousness or mental disorders require adequate nutrition, pelvic organ function control, skin, eye and oral care. It is advisable to use beds with a hydro massage mattress and side bumpers that prevent the patient from falling. In the first days, nutrition is provided by intravenous administration of nutrient solutions, and in the future it is advisable to feed through a nasogastric probe. In patients who are conscious and with normal swallowing, they start eating with liquid food, then switch to taking semi-liquid and ordinary food. If it is impossible to swallow independently, probe feeding is carried out. If swallowing does not recover in 1-2 weeks after a stroke, then the issue of applying a gastrostomy for further nutrition of the patient is resolved [6,7,8].

Laxatives are used to prevent constipation and straining the patient during defecation. In cases of constipation, a cleansing enema should be prescribed at least 1 time a day with sufficient nutrition. Catheterization of the bladder is performed with urinary retention, as well as regularly (every 4-6 hours) in comatose patients. If necessary, a permanent urethral catheter is installed, which is changed once every 3 days.

In 80% of cases, the death of a patient with CEI is associated with complications. In addition to brain edema, hyperthermia and hyperglycemia, pulmonary embolism and deep vein thrombosis are of great danger. Pulmonary embolism is the cause

of death in every fourth patient with CEI. In order to prevent these complications, direct anticoagulants are administered to patients with CEI from the first hours, and antiplatelet agents are used in case of contraindications. With the development or suspicion of deep vein thrombosis or PE, heparin is administered intravenously at a dose of 5000 units, and then 1000 units / hour intravenously or 5000 units subcutaneously every 4-6 hours for 7-10 days under the control of blood clotting time (an increase of 1.5-2 times). In order to prevent thrombosis of the deep veins of the extremities, it is recommended to bandage the legs with an elastic bandage or the use of special (pneumatic compression) stockings, lifting the legs by 6-10 degrees, passive gymnastics (24-48 hours from the moment of the occurrence of MMC).

The duration of bed rest in ischemic stroke is determined by the general condition of the patient, the stability of neurological disorders and vital functions. In cases of satisfactory general condition, with non-progressive neurological disorders and stable hemodynamics, bed rest may be limited to 3-5 days, in other cases it should not exceed 2 weeks, if there are no somatic contraindications. When activating the patient, a gradual increase in physical activity is necessary. As a rule, with a favorable course of AI, after the acute onset of neurological symptoms, its stabilization and gradual regression occur. Active motor, speech and cognitive rehabilitation in the recovery period of AI improves its outcome. Rehabilitation measures should be started as early as possible and systematically carried out at least during the first 6-12 months after AI. During these periods, the rate of restoration of lost functions is maximum.

However, it has been shown that rehabilitation measures have a positive effect at a later date.

Cardiologists and resuscitators should participate in the basic therapy.

II. Differentiated (specific) therapy in the acute period of CEI.

The main provisions. In a specialized neurological hospital with a CT or MRI diagnosis of ischemic stroke, specific therapy can be presented in the form of a number of provisions

* In the first 3-4.5 hours from the onset of stroke, intravenous or intraarterial thrombolysis is performed according to indications, and if there are contraindications, aspirin (or anticoagulants according to indications) is prescribed.

* More than 6 hours from the onset of stroke - aspirin and / or anticoagulants are prescribed according to indications. After thrombolysis, aspirin or anticoagulants are prescribed after 24 hours.

* The use of neuroprotective and reparative drugs is a promising area of treatment, but there is currently no reliable evidence of the effectiveness of the drugs used for this purpose.

* Administration of vasoactive drugs is fraught with the development, in particular, of theft syndromes, and aggravation of cerebral ischemia. They should be used under constant control of the clinical situation and with a Dopplerographic assessment of the state of blood circulation in dynamics.

* Decompressive craniotomy has no absolute indications due to the lack of a reliable evidence base of influence on stroke outcomes, and is possible with pronounced, increasing edema-dislocation of the brain.

* A promising direction is selective intraarterial thrombus removal, the use of which is practically at the experimental stage.

Neuroprotective therapy is carried out in order to increase the survival of neurons in conditions of ischemia and hypoxia.

To prevent the death of viable neurons near the focus of infarction (in the area of "ischemic penumbra"), vasoactive and neurometabolic drugs are prescribed. Although their effectiveness is debatable, their use is advisable, especially when used in the first hours of a stroke, that is, during the "therapeutic window".

Antioxidants are used for neuroprotection: mexidol is used intravenously for the first 10-14 days, 200-500 mg 2-4 times a day, then 200-250 mg 2-3 times a day for 2 weeks; emoxypine 300-600 mg intravenously drop 1 - 3 times a day for 5-15 days; alpha-tocopherol acetate (vitamin E) 0.2 g 2 times a day orally or intramuscularly.

Conclusion. Thus, the treatment of CEI should be comprehensive and include measures aimed at maintaining vital functions, adequate management of existing cardiovascular and other somatic diseases, restoration of cerebral blood flow and neuroprotection. An important role in the treatment of CEI is played by antiplatelet drugs, which should be prescribed already in the first hours after the onset of symptoms of AI. The use of thrombolysis and the latest recanalization methods improve the prognosis of CEI. And such minimally invasive interventions as percutaneous transcatheter occlusion of the auricle of the left atrium and percutaneous transcatheter closure of the oval opening will reduce the number of repeated CEI.

References:

1. Khodjiyeva D.T., Nurova Z.H. Optimization of diagnosis and treatment of early neurological complications in cardioembolic stroke// American journal of medicine and medical sciences. – 2021. – P 137-139.
2. Khodjiyeva D.T., Nurova Z.H., Khaydarov N.K., Khaydarova D.K. Optimization of the diagnosis and treatment of early neurological complications in cardio embolic stroke// European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. – 2021. – P 5788-5792.
3. Жумаева Г.А., Рахматова М.Р., Жалолова В.З., Нурова З.Х. Достигнутые успехи в изучении патогенеза и диагностики гипертонической болезни// Новый день в медицине. – 2020. – С 30-34.
4. Nurova Z.H. Diagnosis of a patient with a cardioembolic stroke// Journal for innovative development in pharmaceutical and technical science. – 2021. P 254-256.
5. Nurova Z.H. Treatment of early neurological complications in cardioembolic stroke// Journal for innovative development in pharmaceutical and technical science. – 2021. P 245-248.
6. Nurova Z.H. Optimization of treatment of early neurological complications in cardioembolic stroke. // Middle European Scientific Bulletin. – 2021. – P. 221-223.
7. Нурова З.Х. Лечение ранних неврологических осложнений кардиоэмболического инсульта// Биология и интегративная медицина. – 2021. – С 70-76.
8. Нурова З.Х. Оптимизация лечения ранних неврологических осложнений при кардиоэмболическом инсульте// Тиббиётда янги кун. – 2021. – С 615-617.